

SCARLET

Superconducting CAbles foR sustainabLe Energy Transition

1.09.2022 – 28.02.2027

Call identifier: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Lead partner: SuperGrid Institute

Authors: Christophe CREUSOT, SuperGrid Institute
Alberto BERTINATO, SuperGrid Institute
Pierre-Baptiste STECKLER, SuperGrid Institute
Antonio MORANDI, University of Bologna
Massimo Fabbri, University of Bologna
Pier Luigi Ribani, University of Bologna
Andrea MUSSO, Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico
Giuliano ANGELI, Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico
Marco BOCCHI, Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico

Submission date: 30/04/2024

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
02/04/2024	0.0	Initial version
30/04/2024	1.0	Submitted version

This document only reflects the authors' view. The programme authorities are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

INDEX

INDEX	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 INTRODUCTION	6
2 DESCRIPTION OF THE ELECTRICAL SYSTEM	7
2.1 GENERAL SCHEMES	7
2.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROTECTION STRATEGY	8
3 COMPONENTS MODELLING AND MAIN HYPOTHESIS	11
3.1 AC GRID AT THE POINT OF COMMON COUPLING	11
3.2 MMC CONVERTER STATION	12
3.3 WINDMILL CONVERSION CHAIN	12
3.4 STRING CABLES	14
3.5 DC CIRCUIT BREAKERS	14
3.6 AC CIRCUIT BREAKERS	15
3.7 SERIES REACTORS	16
3.8 SC CABLE	16
3.8.1 MODELLING PRINCIPLES	16
3.8.2 HTS CABLE HYPOTHESIS	17
3.8.3 MGB ₂ CABLE HYPOTHESIS	20
3.9 RSFCL	23
3.9.1 MODELING PRINCIPLES	23
3.9.2 MAIN INPUT DATA	24
3.10 CABLE SURGE ARRESTER	25
4 FAULT SIMULATION	25
4.1 POLE TO POLE FAULT	25
4.1.1 FAULT F	25
4.1.1.1 Determination of the series reactor value	25
4.1.1.2 Impact on the DC CB	27
4.1.2 RSFCL WORST CASE, FAULT D4	27

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.1.3	SC CABLE FAULT	28
4.1.3.1	50 kVdc network	29
4.1.3.2	25 kVdc network	36
4.1.4	WIND MILL CLUSTER STRING CABLE FAULT B2	50
4.1.4.1	50 kVdc system	51
4.1.4.2	25 kVdc system	52
4.2	POLE TO GROUND FAULT	54
4.2.1	50 kVDC PRODUCTION CASE	55
4.2.1.1	Fault D4 at the onshore extremity of SC cable	55
4.2.1.2	Fault D1, 25 km away from the onshore cable extremity	56
4.2.1.3	Fault C at the offshore extremity of SC cable	57
4.2.2	25 kVDC PRODUCTION CASE	58
4.3	SYNTHESIS ON THE DCCBs	60
5	CONCLUSION	61
6	BIBLIOGRAPHY	63

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this SCARLET deliverable is to simulate and evaluate the protection strategy associated with the electrical scheme that was proposed in SCARLET deliverable D5.1, dealing with the transfer of 1 GW in Medium Voltage Direct Current using a superconducting cable.

The simulations were conducted for the two system voltages of ± 50 kVdc and ± 25 kVdc, in EMTP-RV, a software specialized in the simulation of transient phenomena in electrical grids. To do so, all the components were modeled:

- AC/DC conversion station with its equivalent electrical model and an average arm model for its control;
- Superconducting cable with:
 - o its full electrical model comprising direct and mutual inductances as well as temperature, current and magnetic field dependencies to describe its internal conductor resistance;
 - o One variant of cable structure for the ± 50 kVdc HTS cable;
 - o Two variants of cable structures for the ± 25 kVdc MgB₂ cable;
- Mechanical Direct Current Circuit Breakers with two fault neutralisation time hypotheses;
- Resistive Fault Current Limiter;
- Equivalent load for the “Consumption case”;
- Equivalent windfarm clusters for the “Production case”;
- Other protection devices like surge arresters, series reactors.

The outcome of these simulations will guide system designers in their choices for the protection of the electrical network, the optimisation of power transfer continuity, and superconducting cable protection.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

1 INTRODUCTION

SCARLET proposes to use superconducting (SC) cables to transfer large quantities of power (GW range) in Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) rather than High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC), as is the actual practice. SCARLET deliverable D5.1 investigated the feasibility of such 1 GW MVDC connections [1].

Compared to HVDC connections, two main differences can be highlighted that justify a different approach to the electrical system protection:

- The MVDC conversion station will have a parallel converter architecture: in order to match the high nominal current, several MMC converters will be installed in parallel. Each MMC converter will in turn consist of a certain number of submodules connected in series to match the pole-to-pole rated voltage. Due to this parallel converter architecture, each parallel branch can naturally be isolated if one of them faces a fault.
- Since the proposed cable is superconducting, it has a nonlinear electrical behaviour depending on its operating temperature, current and magnetic field. It also needs to be maintained at cryogenic temperatures using a flow of liquid nitrogen or liquid hydrogen – depending on the type of superconducting material used. The electrical interaction between the cable and the rest of the network could vary in the event of fault; consequently, its behaviour has to be monitored/simulated in terms of both network design and SC cable design.

For these reasons, it is proposed to investigate the network behaviour in case of faults, implementing some rules of protection using Direct Current Circuit Breakers (DCCB) as well as Resistive Superconducting Fault Current Limiters (RSFCL) as the main protection devices. In this investigation, the protection time of the DCCB is considered and its influence on the whole protection strategy is assessed.

In the event of a pole-to-pole fault, a deep and complex interdependency among protection time, RSFCL characteristics and SC cable (including design variants) is foreseen. Thus, to assess properly the corresponding fault currents and the SC cable behaviour, detailed modeling of the main components is necessary.

Other protection functions are investigated, in particular the role of series reactance in the converter station and the requirements for pole-to-ground surge arresters in case of pole-to-ground faults.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE ELECTRICAL SYSTEM

2.1 General schemes

The general concept and purpose of the study was described in Deliverable D5.1. More precisely, four schemes are considered corresponding to the two system voltages of ± 50 kVdc and ± 25 kVdc on one side and “Production” (Figure 1) or “Consumption” (Figure 2) configurations.

The SC cable is integrated in a medium-voltage electrical network that consists of:

- Modular Multi-level Converters (MMC) station (including MMC converters and power transformers);
- Resistive Superconducting Fault Current Limiter (RSFCL);
- Superconducting cable (SC);
- Direct Current Circuit Breakers for both Offshore- and Onshore-stations;
- Conventional cable connecting the Offshore Wind Generation group and the Offshore-substation;
- Offshore Wind Generation groups;
- Onshore AC sources (ideal voltage generator behind a short circuit impedance).

Figure 1. Production scheme

Figure 2. Consumption scheme

For the production configuration, the case study consists of exporting 1 GW of offshore wind power distributed in five clusters of 200 MW each.

For the consumption configuration, the case study is more generic, where one single 1 GW load is considered.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

2.2 Description of the protection strategy

The MVDC conversion station architecture naturally offers the possibility of isolating one faulty converter while continuing the operation with the remaining converters.

This is also valid in the operation of an offshore wind park consisting of parallel clusters: one faulty cluster can be isolated while keeping the other ones in operation.

This parallel architecture of the converter station and the wind park allows the operation at reduced power under certain circumstances if a fault occurs in the conversion station or in one cluster. This protection principle is called “the selective strategy”. On the opposite, in case the fault is on a collection DC bus bar or on the cable itself, transmission will be stopped.

Figure 3. Fault mapping on the production case

To achieve a selective strategy on the conversion station side, a reactor (DCR) is inserted in series with the DCCB in each converter branch. The DCR is sized for the “Fault F case” where one DCCB has to interrupt the current supplied by N-1 converters plus the contribution from the wind farm.

For this kind of DC grid architecture topology (fault behaviour as for the asymmetric monopole) pole-to-ground faults entail higher short circuit currents and lower overvoltage transients; viceversa pole-to-ground faults entail higher overvoltages and lower short circuit currents. The pole-to-pole fault cases and their corresponding protection sequences are summarized in [Table 1](#), the fault points refer to [Figure 3](#). It is worth noting that pole-to-ground faults will trigger the same protection sequence as for the pole-to-pole faults. For each fault location, two cases are considered that are distinguished in the “Description of simulation” column:

- The primary protection case, *i.e.* the primary sequence that should normally occur in the event of a fault.
- The backup protection case, *i.e.* the backup protection sequence when the designated primary protection fails.

This backup protection is necessarily slower than the primary protection, therefore, it is the sizing sequence of several components, especially the SC cable but also the RSFCL.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Table 1: Summary of pole-to-pole fault cases and their protection scenarios

Fault point	Description of fault	Protection objectives/consequences	Description of simulation	Circuit breaker in action	Expected results
F	Pole to Pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at the MVDC terminal of MMC1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - remove fault current contribution from MMC1 - maintain the power transfer via the other MMCs 	<u>Primary protection:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the Onshore-DC circuit breaker DCCB01 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DCCB01_On Sh 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sizing of DCR - energy to be absorbed by the DCCB ZnO
F	Pole to Pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at the MVDC terminal of MMC1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stop the power transfer 	<u>Back-up protection:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failure of the Onshore-DC CB DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all the Onshore-DCCBs - Blocking MMC converters in case of DCCB01_OnSh failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Offshore-DCCBs - All the Onshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_On Sh - all ACCB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short time current of the DCCB and DCR
E	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative Onshore-DC busbars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stop the power transfer 	<u>Primary protection:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all the Onshore-DCCBs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Offshore-DCCBs - All the Onshore-DCCBs - all ACCB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximum prospective current of the SC cable -
E	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative Onshore-DC busbars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stop the power transfer 	<u>Back-up protection:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failure of the Onshore-DCCB DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all the other healthy Onshore-DCCBs - Blocking MMC converters in case of DCCB01_OnSh failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Offshore-DCCBs - All the Onshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_On Sh - all ACCB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum prospective current of the SC cable
D4	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at the onshore-terminals of the superconducting cable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stop the power transfer 	<u>Primary protection:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all the Onshore-DCCBs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Offshore-DCCBs - All the Onshore-DCCBs - all ACCB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL
D4	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at the onshore-terminals of the superconducting cable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stop the power transfer 	<u>Back-up protection:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failure of the Onshore-DC circuit breaker DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all the Onshore-DCCBs - Blocking MMC converters in case of DCCB01_OnSh failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Offshore-DCCBs - All the Onshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_On Sh - all ACCB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Fault point	Description of fault	Protection objectives/consequences	Description of simulation	Circuit breaker in action	Expected results
D2	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at 500 m from beginning of the cable	- stop the power transfer	<u>Primary protection:</u> - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs	- All Offshore-DCCBs - All Onshore-DCCBs - all ACCB	- current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL - Current stress on the SC cable portions - Determine the short time and peak withstand current of the SC cable.
D2	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at 500 m	- stop the power transfer - avoid an irreversible degradation of SC cable portions away from the defect location	<u>Back-up protection:</u> - Failure of the Onshore-DCCB DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs - Blocking MMC converters in case of DCCB01_OnSh failure	- All Offshore-DCCBs - All Onshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_OnSh - all ACCB	- current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL - Current stress on the SC cable portions
D1	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at 25 km	- stop the power transfer - avoid an irreversible degradation of SC cable portions away from the defect location	<u>Primary protection:</u> - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs	- All Offshore-DCCBs - All Onshore-DCCBs - all ACCB	- current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL - Current stress on the SC cable portions
D1	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at 25 km	- stop the power transfer - avoid an irreversible degradation of SC cable portions away from the defect location	<u>Back-up protection:</u> - Failure of the Onshore-DCCB DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs - Blocking MMC converters in case of DCCB01_OnSh failure	- All Offshore-DCCBs - All Onshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_OnSh - all ACCB	- current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL - Current stress on the SC cable portions
C	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative Offshore-DC busbars	- stop the power transfer - avoid degradation of the SC cable	<u>Primary protection:</u> - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs	- All Offshore-DCCBs - All Onshore-DCCBs - all ACCB	- current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL - Current stress on the SC cable
C	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative Offshore-DC busbars	- stop the power transfer - avoid degradation of the SC cable	<u>Back-up protection:</u> - Failure of the Onshore-DCCB DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs - Blocking MMC	- All Offshore-DCCBs - All Onshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_OnSh	- current through the SC cable - energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL - Current stress on the SC cable

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Fault point	Description of fault	Protection objectives/consequences	Description of simulation	Circuit breaker in action	Expected results
			converters in case of DCCB01_OnSh failure	- all ACCB	
B2	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at the offshore-terminal of the string cable	- remove contribution from the faulty cluster - maintain the power transfer from the other clusters	<u>Primary protection:</u> - Open Offshore-DCCB01	- Offshore-DCCB01	- energy to be absorbed by the offshore DCCB ZnO - Determine if a DCR is necessary on offshore side
B2	Pole-to-pole fault between the positive and negative DC poles at the offshore-terminal of the string cable	- stop the power transfer - avoid degradation of the SC cable	<u>Back-up protection:</u> - Failure of the Offshore-DCCB DCCB01_OnSh - Open all Offshore-DCCBs - Open all Onshore-DCCBs	- All Offshore-DCCBs except DCCB01_OnSh - All Onshore-DCCBs	- energy to be absorbed by the Offshore DCCB ZnO

The first step for setting properly all the system parameters is to start with the definition of the series reactor with Fault F. Once this is set, the next step is to fix the RSFCL parameters in the case of Fault D4 with failure of the MMC01 DCCB, that should lead to the RSFCL worst case.

Then, the simulation plan can continue with the Faults D2 and C, to finish with B2.

3 COMPONENTS MODELLING AND MAIN HYPOTHESIS

In this section, the different components of the network will be reviewed and their main design hypothesis will be described. These hypotheses are used for the modelling into EMTP-RV environment.

3.1 AC Grid at the point of common coupling

To transfer the 1GW-Wind production, the 400kV-AC grid is selected based on the feedbacks from the large offshore wind farm projects in Europe. The following table shows the short-circuit current and the ratio X/R at point of common coupling (PCC) between the 400kV-AC grid and the Onshore-MMCs station.

Table 2: Parameters of the equivalent AC grid

Parameters	Unit	Value
Short-circuit power	MVA	10000
Ratio X/R	-	6,28
Nominal voltage	kV	400
Frequency	Hz	50

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

3.2 MMC Converter station

The Conversion station consists of several parallel Modular Multi-level Converters (Symmetric monopoles). They are simulated in EMTP-RV using an arm average arm model. Table 3 summarizes the physical components and electrical characteristics of the MMC converters and the power transformers.

Table 3: Technical specifications of the main components in the MMC station

Parameters	Unit	Value (± 25kVdc)	Value (± 50kVdc)
Number of MMC station	-	8	4
MMC Station			
Rated power	MVA	125	250
DC pole-to-pole voltage	kV	50	100
AC primary voltage	kVrms	400	400
AC secondary voltage	kVrms	30	60
Frequency	Hz	50	50
Transformer reactance	pu	0.15	0.15
Transformer resistance	pu	0.005	0.005
MMC Converter			
MMC arm inductance	pu	0.15	0.15
Capacitance of submodule	mF	15	15
Number of submodules per arm	num	22	44
Conduction resistance of each SM	Ω	0.001	0.001

3.3 Windmill conversion chain

In this project, the wind farm is assumed to be composed by several cluster of 200MW-Offshore Wind Generation units, as schematized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. 200 MW offshore wind generation

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 5. Proposed conversion chain architecture for DC collection.

Thus, five groups of Offshore Wind Generation are required to generate 1 GW in total into the AC-grid. From Figure 5 it is observed that each Offshore Wind Generation group includes wind turbine generators and the conversion chain from AC current to DC current with the help of the AC/DC and DC/DC converters. The Table 4 shows the main data of the 200MW-Offshore Wind Generation group depending on the level voltage:

Table 4: Main data of the 200 MW offshore wind generation group

Parameters	Unit	Value (±25kV)	Value (±50kV)
Power transmission	MW	200	200
Nominal current	A	4000	2000
Nominal voltage	kV	25	50

A simplified model of the Offshore Wind Generation Group is implemented in EMTP-RV (Figure 6). The aim of the modelling model is to check that the current from the wind production can be maintained in all system operating conditions (normal operation and transient operation, i.e. when there is a fault in the system). In the simulation, a first phase is dedicated to reach the steady state current in the system before moving to the second phase, where the short circuit is simulated. To manage the ramp-up of the current into the SC cable in the first phase, the “Ramp current source” model is selected in the EMTP-RV library. The ideal voltage source V_{CL} provides the maximum pole to pole voltage of the windmill cluster.

Figure 6. Simplified model of the 200 MW offshore wind generation group

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

3.4 String cables

The string cables are designed based on the requirement of the power transmission (200 MW for each group of production) at the MVDC voltages (± 25 kVdc and ± 50 kVdc). The assumptions for the electrical and geometrical parameters of the ± 25 kVdc and ± 50 kVdc cables are summarized in Table 5. Based on these parameters, a Constant Parameter cable model of 4 phases and 3 km long is set in EMTP-RV.

Table 5: Electrical and geometrical parameters of the string cables

Nominal voltage	± 25 kVdc	± 50 kVdc
Number of cables per pole	2	1
Conductor (mm²)		
Cross section (mm ²)	2500	2500
Nominal current (A)	2200	2200
Resistivity (Ω .m)	$1.72e^{-8}$	$1.72e^{-8}$
Radius (mm)	28	28
Insulation		
Thickness (mm)	5.6	11.9
Permittivity	2.5	2.5
Tangent delta	0.004	0.004
Screen		
Thickness (mm)	2	2
Resistivity(Ω .m)	$1.72e^{-8}$	$1.72e^{-8}$
Internal diameter(mm)	34.6	40.9
External diameter(mm)	36.6	42.9
Jacket		
Thickness(mm)	3	3
Permittivity	2.5	2.5
Tangent delta	0.004	0.004
External diameter(mm)	39.6	45.9

3.5 DC Circuit Breakers

The type of DC circuit breaker selected for this study is a mechanical breaker assisted with current injection (Figure 7). The main path consists in a vacuum interrupter (VI) operated by a drive. A parallel LC branch with a pre-charged capacitor is ready to inject a medium frequency current – typically in the range 1 kHz to 5 kHz – upon the closing of a making switch. The third parallel branch is a zinc oxide varistor that will absorb the circuit magnetic energy after the vacuum interrupter clears the injected current superimposed to the fault current. Two variants are considered, one operating and neutralizing the fault current in less than 5 ms, while the other has to act in less than 20 ms. Practically, the faster one uses a vacuum interrupter operated by a THOMSON type electromagnetic actuator and the making switch is typically a plasma triggered gap. The slower one uses a vacuum interrupter operated by a standard mechanical drive used by MVAC or HVAC circuit breaker, the making switch is a mechanical switch, also operated by a standard MVAC or HVAC mechanical drive.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

A main hypothesis for the simulation is the fault breaking current of the DCCBs: a performance of 20 kA is selected but a safety of 20 % is used as a hypothesis in the simulation, resulting in breaking the current at 16 kA even though the LC loop is designed for an interruption of 20 kA.

Figure 7. Electrical schematic of the DC CB

One output of the simulation will be the specification of the energy to be absorbed by the Zinc oxide varistor.

The table below summarizes the DC CB parameters used for the simulation.

Table 6: Main DC CB parameters

System voltage	U_n	± 25 kVDC	± 25 kVDC	± 50 kVDC	± 50 kVDC
Nominal current	I_n	2500 A	2500 A	2500 A	2500 A
Effective Breaking current	I_{bk}	16 kA	16 kA	16 kA	16 kA
Fault Neutralisation time	t_{bk}	5 ms	20 ms	5 ms	20 ms
Capacitance	C	34 μ F	34 μ F	17 μ F	17 μ F
Capacitance pre-charging voltage	U_{c0}	25 kVDC	25 kVDC	50 kVDC	50 kVDC
Inductance	L_{osc}	34 μ H	34 μ H	93 μ H	93 μ H
Stray resistance	R_{osc}	0,34 mOhm	0,34 mOhm	0,93 mOhm	0,93 mOhm
ZnO clipping voltage	U_{prot}	1,6 pu	1,6 pu	1,6 pu	1,6 pu

3.6 AC Circuit breakers

The converter AC circuit breakers will be triggered via a protection algorithm inside the converter station, meaning that their breaking time is considered in this study as 3 cycles, *i.e.* 60 ms (including relaying time, opening time and arcing time).

On the other hand, the Grid AC breakers have protection schemes outside the converter station and will have a slower breaking time. In this study, it will be considered as 150 ms.

Both converter AC breakers and Grid AC breakers are sized for a rated voltage of 420 kV. Devices sized for rated short circuit currents of 40 kA to 63 kA are widely commercially available, largely overpassing the requirement.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

3.7 Series reactors

Reactors in series with the DC breakers are used in the protection scheme inside the converter station. To obtain more reliable simulations, the magnetic energy dissipation has to be considered in DC fault scenarios; thus, realistic reactor resistances are considered with L/R ratio of 650 ms. This value is used also for the internal MMC converter arm reactors.

3.8 SC Cable

3.8.1 Modelling principles

The principles of the SC cable proper modelling for transient current analysis were detailed in [2]. It does not only describe the method to implement the electro-thermal behaviour of the conductive layers, but it also describes the magnetic coupling of the parallel conductive layers.

Three types of cables are described; they consist of one concentric HTS monopole cable (Figure 8 (a)), one MgB₂ concentric monopole cable (Figure 8 (b)) and one MgB₂ “transposed petals” monopole cable (Figure 8 (c)).

Figure 8. Views of the 3 superconducting cable types

The respective Cable parameters used for the study are described in Chapters 3.8.2 and 3.8.3.

The common practice for HVDC cables is to ground the cable shield at its two extremities. Also, a grounding is considered as good quality if the grounding resistance does not exceed 1 Ohm.

In this study, the same approach will be applied for any of the configuration: the cable shield is grounded at its two extremities via a 1 Ohm resistor.

To improve the installation cost efficiency, the two cable poles should be installed in the same trench; this is also a common request in HVDC to have “bundled” cable poles because it minimizes the apparent external magnetic field. Again, in this study, the same approach is applied. As a consequence, the inductance matrix has to be calculated considering the magnetic coupling between the two cable poles. If one pole contains N parallel conductors, the inductance matrix of one independent pole will be of size N x N. Now, considering the two poles coupling, the inductance matrix of the combined two-poles system is of size 2 N x 2 N.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

3.8.2 HTS Cable hypothesis

Several hypotheses are considered to complete the electro-thermal model of this cable. First, a temperature gradient along the offshore cable is applied with the hypothesis of a typical hydraulic length of 25 km, meaning that, for example, one cryogenic machine can deal with 25 km long cable outward flow on the positive pole and a return flow through the negative pole [1].

With the hypothesis of a constant cryostat thermal loss, an outward temperature of 67 K and an inward temperature of 77 K, the temperature gradient can be considered linear with the cable pole length in this temperature range as shown in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9. Illustration of the temperature gradient along the SC offshore cable

Then, the individual tape critical current dependence on magnetic field and temperature is taken into account based on THEVA Proline 2G HTS reference in the “High-Temperature superconducting wire critical current database” [3]. The critical current is normalized to its self-field value at 77 K (**Table 7**).

Table 7: Synthesis of the relative critical current ratio based on temperature and magnetic field

T [K] B _{90°} [mT]	0	30	50	70	100	150	200	300
65	2,0039	2,0257	2,0186	2,0044	1,9809	1,9065	1,7533	1,5410
67,5	1,7948	1,8095	1,8055	1,7929	1,7508	1,6488	1,5291	1,2856
70	1,5851	1,5993	1,5925	1,5753	1,5331	1,4326		1,0874
72,5	1,3785	1,3907	1,3783	1,3670	1,3168	1,2122	1,0968	0,8969
75	1,1668	1,1848	1,1865	1,1671	1,1132	1,0072	0,9044	0,7223
77	1,0000	1,0069	0,9977	0,9741	0,9212	0,8185	0,7233	0,5758
77,5	0,9583	0,9624	0,9505	0,9259	0,8732	0,7714	0,6780	0,5392
80	0,7521	0,7642	0,7547	0,7233	0,6706	0,5804	0,4935	0,3846
82,5	0,5514	0,5479	0,5272	0,4993	0,4585	0,3788	0,3219	0,2458
85	0,3686	0,3523	0,3360	0,3114	0,2668	0,2160	0,1810	0,1360
87,5	0,1983	0,1793	0,1580	0,1402	0,1186	0,0935	0,0765	0,0556
90	0,0700	0,0514	0,0423	0,0358	0,0284	0,0216	0,0169	0,0117

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

The n-value, equal to 23, is implemented in the model, taken from the same database.

For each HTS layer, the perpendicular magnetic field is calculated at its nominal current (2500 A), the self-field tape critical current at 77 K is set as the reference and the geometry of the tape are provided by NEXANS.

To complete the tape description, its normal resistance and specific heat are defined based on the tape geometry and material properties (Figure 10).

Figure 10. HTS tape normal resistance and heat capacitance

The copper former and copper shield are represented with their temperature-dependant characteristics specific resistance and heat capacitance (Figure 11).

Figure 11. HTS cable former and shield resistance (left) and heat capacitance (right)

Though the cryostat walls are highly resistive, their resistances are introduced as well but only with constant values, no thermal calculation is carried out for these two conductors.

Table 8: Cryostat resistances

Parameter	Unit	Value
R_{in}	mOhm/m	2,01
R_{out}	mOhm/m	1,12

Three capacitances are evaluated: capacitance between the inner wall and outer wall of the cryostat (C_{vacuum}), capacitance between the shield and the inner wall of the cryostat ($C_{coolant}$) and capacitance between the 4th HTS layer and the shield (C_{solid}).

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Table 9: SC cable capacitances

Parameter	Unit	Value
C_{vacuum}	nF/m	0,129
C_{coolant}	nF/m	0,0585
C_{solid}	nF/m	1,09

Finally, the 16x16 inductance matrix is calculated considering coupled monopole cables **Table 10**

Table 10: inductance matrix of the 2 coupled monopole cables. Inductances are expressed in H/m

		CABLE 1								CABLE 2							
		Former	HTS1	HTS2	HTS3	HTS4	Shield	Pipe Int	Pipe Ext	Former	HTS1	HTS2	HTS3	HTS4	Shield	Pipe Int	Pipe Ext
CABLE 1	Former	6.9615E-07	5.0956E-07	5.1941E-07	5.2532E-07	5.3447E-07	5.3571E-07	2.9092E-07	2.2175E-07	6.5463E-08	5.2757E-08	5.4319E-08	5.5961E-08	5.7524E-08	6.5558E-08	6.6954E-08	6.7281E-08
	HTS1	5.0956E-07	5.5464E-07	5.3145E-07	5.3857E-07	5.1097E-07	4.4562E-07	2.3606E-07	1.7961E-07	5.2757E-08	4.4726E-08	4.5779E-08	4.6866E-08	4.7886E-08	5.2828E-08	5.3039E-08	5.3364E-08
	HTS2	5.1941E-07	5.3145E-07	5.5426E-07	5.3130E-07	5.3895E-07	4.4874E-07	2.4347E-07	1.8518E-07	5.4320E-08	4.5779E-08	4.6888E-08	4.8040E-08	4.9118E-08	5.4397E-08	5.4612E-08	5.4948E-08
	HTS3	5.2532E-07	5.3857E-07	5.3130E-07	5.5469E-07	5.3202E-07	4.7498E-07	2.5109E-07	1.9091E-07	5.5961E-08	4.6866E-08	4.8040E-08	4.9256E-08	5.0403E-08	5.6041E-08	5.6265E-08	5.6612E-08
	HTS4	5.3447E-07	5.1097E-07	5.3895E-07	5.3202E-07	5.5508E-07	4.7578E-07	2.5814E-07	1.9623E-07	5.7524E-08	4.7886E-08	4.9118E-08	5.0403E-08	5.1611E-08	5.7612E-08	5.7840E-08	5.8196E-08
	Shield	5.3571E-07	4.4562E-07	4.4874E-07	4.7498E-07	4.7578E-07	5.4374E-07	2.8812E-07	2.1989E-07	6.5558E-08	5.2828E-08	5.4397E-08	5.6041E-08	5.7612E-08	6.5673E-08	6.5930E-08	6.6324E-08
	Pipe Int	2.9092E-07	2.3606E-07	2.4347E-07	2.5109E-07	2.5814E-07	2.8812E-07	4.5204E-07	3.2111E-07	6.6955E-08	5.3039E-08	5.4612E-08	5.6265E-08	5.7840E-08	6.5930E-08	9.7245E-08	9.6341E-08
	Pipe Ext	2.2175E-07	1.7961E-07	1.8518E-07	1.9091E-07	1.9623E-07	2.1989E-07	3.2111E-07	3.4965E-07	6.7283E-08	5.3364E-08	5.4948E-08	5.6612E-08	5.8196E-08	6.6324E-08	9.6338E-08	9.6218E-08
CABLE 2	Former	6.5463E-08	5.2757E-08	5.4320E-08	5.5961E-08	5.7524E-08	6.5558E-08	6.6955E-08	6.7283E-08	6.9615E-07	5.0956E-07	5.1941E-07	5.2532E-07	5.3447E-07	5.3571E-07	2.9092E-07	2.2175E-07
	HTS1	5.2757E-08	4.4726E-08	4.5779E-08	4.6866E-08	4.7886E-08	5.2828E-08	5.3039E-08	5.3364E-08	5.0956E-07	5.5464E-07	5.3145E-07	5.3857E-07	5.1097E-07	4.4562E-07	2.3606E-07	1.7961E-07
	HTS2	5.4320E-08	4.5779E-08	4.6888E-08	4.8040E-08	4.9118E-08	5.4397E-08	5.4612E-08	5.4948E-08	5.1941E-07	5.3145E-07	5.5426E-07	5.3130E-07	5.3895E-07	4.4874E-07	2.4347E-07	1.8518E-07
	HTS3	5.5961E-08	4.6866E-08	4.8040E-08	4.9256E-08	5.0403E-08	5.6041E-08	5.6265E-08	5.6612E-08	5.2532E-07	5.3857E-07	5.3130E-07	5.5469E-07	5.3202E-07	4.7498E-07	2.5109E-07	1.9091E-07
	HTS4	5.7524E-08	4.7886E-08	4.9118E-08	5.0403E-08	5.1611E-08	5.7612E-08	5.7840E-08	5.8196E-08	5.3447E-07	5.1097E-07	5.3895E-07	5.3202E-07	5.5508E-07	4.7578E-07	2.5814E-07	1.9623E-07
	Shield	6.5558E-08	5.2828E-08	5.4397E-08	5.6041E-08	5.7612E-08	6.5673E-08	6.5930E-08	6.6324E-08	5.3571E-07	4.4562E-07	4.4874E-07	4.7498E-07	4.7578E-07	5.4374E-07	2.8812E-07	2.1989E-07
	Pipe Int	6.6954E-08	5.3039E-08	5.4612E-08	5.6265E-08	5.7840E-08	6.5930E-08	9.7245E-08	9.6338E-08	2.9092E-07	2.3606E-07	2.4347E-07	2.5109E-07	2.5814E-07	2.8812E-07	4.5204E-07	3.2111E-07
	Pipe Ext	6.7281E-08	5.3364E-08	5.4948E-08	5.6612E-08	5.8196E-08	6.6324E-08	9.6341E-08	9.6218E-08	2.2175E-07	1.7961E-07	1.8518E-07	1.9091E-07	1.9623E-07	2.1989E-07	3.2111E-07	3.4965E-07

A series resistance of 1 μOhm per km of tape layer is added to be more representative of series junction resistance that are inevitable. However, being this value very small, internal loops between layers will behave in a way that will necessarily take a very long time for the current to equilibrate during the cable charging. As for the simulation, it is first necessary to reach the steady state of the current flow before establishing the fault, and simulations are time consuming (since a long-time interval need to be simulated for reaching a balanced current distribution between layers) and memory consuming. To save calculation time and memory, a series resistance of 100 mOhm is inserted in each tape layer and it is bypassed just before the setting of the fault.

To account for the LN_2 temperature distribution along the cable, a split of the 100 km cable in several series connected portions is implemented with one 75 km portion & nine times 2,5 km portions & one 2 km section and one 0,5 km portion. The short 500 m portion allows the creation of the fault D2, while the other portions of 2k m and 2,5 km allow a discretisation of the 25 km hydraulic length. Each of this portion is described with the two coupled poles and the respective positive and negative poles temperature distribution according to **Figure 9**.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 12. HTS cable of 100 km length split into 12 portions in series

As it can be seen in **Figure 12**, the features to create a pole to pole or pole to ground fault are inserted to create a fault located 500 m from the right-hand extremity and 25 km from the right-hand extremity. **Figure 13** shows a magnified view of the SC fault creator: a switch is inserted between each neighbouring conductors. In the case of a pole-to-pole faults, all the switches are turned on at the desired instant of the fault. In case of a Pole to Ground fault, only the switches related to the faulty pole are turned on.

Figure 13. Zoom on the SC cable fault scheme

3.8.3 MgB₂ Cable hypothesis

A temperature of 20 K is imposed, no gradient along the cable is considered. Similarly to the HTS cable, the dependency of the critical current of the MgB₂ wire upon temperature and magnetic field is implemented into the model as well as the wire normal resistance and specific heat. The data used to express this relationship are exposed in **Table 11**, where the self-field critical current at 25 K is taken as the reference. These data are supplied by ASG Superconductors.

Table 11: Table of relative critical current with respect to temperature and magnetic field

T [K] B90° [mT]	0	200	400	500	600	800	900	1000	1200	1400	1600	1800
15	2,475	2,157	1,838	1,670	1,498	1,278	1,158	1,036	0,878	0,741	0,616	0,516
20	1,711	1,490	1,270	1,154	1,036	0,884	0,800	0,716	0,581	0,463	0,371	0,282
25	1,000	0,871	0,742	0,674	0,605	0,460	0,394	0,343	0,249	0,174	0,115	0,071
26	0,929	0,800	0,671	0,603	0,534	0,389	0,322	0,271	0,177	0,102	0,044	0,000
27	0,857	0,728	0,599	0,531	0,462	0,317	0,251	0,200	0,106	0,031	0,000	0,000
28	0,786	0,657	0,528	0,460	0,391	0,246	0,179	0,129	0,034	0,000	0,000	0,000
29	0,714	0,585	0,457	0,389	0,320	0,175	0,108	0,057	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

30	0,643	0,514	0,385	0,317	0,248	0,103	0,036	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
31	0,571	0,443	0,314	0,246	0,177	0,032	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
32	0,500	0,371	0,242	0,174	0,105	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
33	0,429	0,300	0,171	0,103	0,034	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
34	0,357	0,228	0,099	0,031	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
35	0,286	0,157	0,028	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
36	0,214	0,085	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
37	0,143	0,014	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
38	0,071	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
39	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000

The wire resistance and specific heat are considered as those displayed in [Figure 14](#).

Figure 14. MgB₂ wire resistance and heat capacitance

The self-field critical current of the wire is assumed with a value of 1487 A at 20 K. Its temperature and magnetic field dependencies are also included in the model.

The capacitances, cryostat wall resistances and inductance matrices are specific to the concentric design and to the transposed petal design, the parameters are listed below. Due to the cable structure, the concentric one has a 10 x 10 inductance matrix ([Table 14](#)) and the transposed petal one has a 12 x 12 inductance matrix ([Table 15](#)) because of the additional petal centre conductor.

Table 12: Cryostat resistances

Parameter	Unit	Concentric design	Transposed petal design
C_{vacuum}	nF/m	0,132	0,134
C_{coolant}	nF/m	0,14	0,195
C_{solid}	nF/m	0,64	1,24

Table 13: Cable capacitances

Parameter	Unit	Concentric design	Transposed petal design
C_{vacuum}	nF/m	0,132	0,134
C_{coolant}	nF/m	0,14	0,195
C_{solid}	nF/m	0,64	1,24

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Table 14: inductance matrix of the 2 coupled concentric monopole cables. Inductances are expressed in H/m

		Cable 1					Cable 2				
		Former	MgB2	Shield	Pipe Int	Pipe Ext	Former	MgB2	Shield	Pipe Int	Pipe Ext
Cable 1	Former	7,3907E-07	6,6411E-07	5,7138E-07	4,7089E-07	3,9113E-07	1,5856E-07	1,5852E-07	1,5858E-07	1,6087E-07	1,6125E-07
	MgB2	6,6411E-07	6,6287E-07	5,6846E-07	4,6363E-07	3,8565E-07	1,5852E-07	1,5854E-07	1,5861E-07	1,5882E-07	1,5924E-07
	Shield	5,7138E-07	5,6846E-07	5,7818E-07	4,6437E-07	3,8610E-07	1,5858E-07	1,5861E-07	1,5866E-07	1,5888E-07	1,5931E-07
	Pipe Int	4,7089E-07	4,6363E-07	4,6437E-07	7,4995E-07	6,0182E-07	1,6086E-07	1,5882E-07	1,5888E-07	2,3567E-07	2,3481E-07
	Pipe Ext	3,9113E-07	3,8565E-07	3,8610E-07	6,0182E-07	6,1050E-07	1,6125E-07	1,5924E-07	1,5931E-07	2,3480E-07	2,3470E-07
Cable 2	Former	1,5856E-07	1,5852E-07	1,5858E-07	1,6086E-07	1,6125E-07	7,3907E-07	6,6411E-07	5,7138E-07	4,7089E-07	3,9113E-07
	MgB2	1,5852E-07	1,5854E-07	1,5861E-07	1,5882E-07	1,5924E-07	6,6411E-07	6,6287E-07	5,6846E-07	4,6363E-07	3,8565E-07
	Shield	1,5858E-07	1,5861E-07	1,5866E-07	1,5888E-07	1,5931E-07	5,7138E-07	5,6846E-07	5,7818E-07	4,6437E-07	3,8610E-07
	Pipe Int	1,6087E-07	1,5882E-07	1,5888E-07	2,3567E-07	2,3480E-07	4,7089E-07	4,6363E-07	4,6437E-07	7,4995E-07	6,0182E-07
	Pipe Ext	1,6125E-07	1,5924E-07	1,5931E-07	2,3481E-07	2,3470E-07	3,9113E-07	3,8565E-07	3,8610E-07	6,0182E-07	6,1050E-07

Table 15: inductance matrix of the 2 coupled transposed petal monopole cables. Inductances are expressed in H/m

		Cable 1						Cable 1					
		Former	Centri Petali	MgB2	Shield	Pipe Int	Pipe Ext	Former	Centri Petali	MgB2	Shield	Pipe Int	Pipe Ext
Cable 1	Former	9,4618E-07	7,5615E-07	7,5522E-07	5,9119E-07	5,2895E-07	4,4625E-07	2,0456E-07	2,0408E-07	2,0408E-07	2,0444E-07	2,0929E-07	2,0973E-07
	Centri Petali	7,5615E-07	7,7788E-07	7,3473E-07	5,9049E-07	5,1160E-07	4,3271E-07	2,0408E-07	2,0385E-07	2,0385E-07	2,0421E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0483E-07
	MgB2	7,5522E-07	7,3473E-07	7,2907E-07	5,9058E-07	5,1163E-07	4,3272E-07	2,0408E-07	2,0385E-07	2,0386E-07	2,0422E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0483E-07
	Shield	5,9119E-07	5,9049E-07	5,9058E-07	5,9661E-07	5,1315E-07	4,3380E-07	2,0444E-07	2,0421E-07	2,0422E-07	2,0457E-07	2,0476E-07	2,0519E-07
	Pipe Int	5,2895E-07	5,1160E-07	5,1163E-07	5,1315E-07	8,4042E-07	6,9000E-07	2,0929E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0476E-07	2,9492E-07	2,9616E-07
Cable 1	Pipe Ext	4,4625E-07	4,3271E-07	4,3272E-07	4,3380E-07	6,9000E-07	6,9494E-07	2,0974E-07	2,0483E-07	2,0483E-07	2,0519E-07	2,9611E-07	2,9800E-07
	Former	2,0456E-07	2,0408E-07	2,0408E-07	2,0444E-07	2,0929E-07	2,0974E-07	9,4618E-07	7,5615E-07	7,5522E-07	5,9119E-07	5,2895E-07	4,4625E-07
	Centri Petali	2,0408E-07	2,0385E-07	2,0385E-07	2,0421E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0483E-07	7,5615E-07	7,7788E-07	7,3473E-07	5,9049E-07	5,1160E-07	4,3271E-07
	MgB2	2,0408E-07	2,0385E-07	2,0386E-07	2,0422E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0483E-07	7,5522E-07	7,3473E-07	7,2907E-07	5,9058E-07	5,1163E-07	4,3272E-07
	Shield	2,0444E-07	2,0421E-07	2,0422E-07	2,0457E-07	2,0476E-07	2,0519E-07	5,9119E-07	5,9049E-07	5,9058E-07	5,9661E-07	5,1315E-07	4,3380E-07
Cable 1	Pipe Int	2,0929E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0440E-07	2,0476E-07	2,9492E-07	2,9611E-07	5,2895E-07	5,1160E-07	5,1163E-07	5,1315E-07	8,4042E-07	6,9000E-07
	Pipe Ext	2,0973E-07	2,0483E-07	2,0483E-07	2,0519E-07	2,9616E-07	2,9800E-07	4,4625E-07	4,3271E-07	4,3272E-07	4,3380E-07	6,9000E-07	6,9494E-07

Finally, the other copper layers are also modelled with temperature dependant resistances (Figure 15) and heat capacitances (Figure 16) with former and shield for the concentric cable and former, shield and petal centre for the transposed petal cable.

(a) concentric cable

(b) transposed petal cable

Figure 15. Resistance of the copper conductors

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 16. Heat capacitance of the copper conductors

In EMTP, the 100 km cable is in fact 100.5 km long for simplicity and it is divided in three portions: one of 75000 m, one of 25000 m and one of 500 m (Figure 17). At each extremity, the shield and the cryostat walls are grounded via a 1 Ohm resistance.

Figure 17. Illustration of the 100.5 km long, petal type cable structure in EMTP-RV

3.9 RSFCL

3.9.1 Modeling principles

The RSFCL is made of wounded bifilar HTS tape coils to minimize its inductance.

The RSFCL model is basically the same as one HTS layer of superconducting cable. The RSFCL model closely resembles a single HTS layer within a superconducting cable.

A tape is considered with its constitutive material layers geometries and material properties. The superconducting layer properties are described with the percolation law to evaluate its conductance

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

based on current and temperature. The other tape layers are described with their temperature-dependant conductance and specific heat.

3.9.2 Main input data

The selected tape is based on the properties of the Shanghai Superconductor tape ST-12-L; its cross section is represented in Figure 18 and it is extracted from [4]. Geometrical data are also reported in the figure.

Figure 18. Cross section of the ST-12-L tape from Shanghai Superconductor. The figure is not to scale.

For the purpose of this study, considering the high nominal current of the RSFCL, a target of 650 A for the self-field critical current at 77 K is considered in the model.

The parameters used for the tape thermo-electrical model are:

Figure 19. RSFCL tape normal resistance (left) and heat capacitance (right)

To coordinate the nominal current of the system and the critical current of the SC cable, the critical current of the RSFCL is set to be 15 % higher than the cable current. This value can be achieved by subcooling the Liquid Nitrogen down to 67 K. The n-value of the tape is set to 28.

The total length of HTS tape will be a parameter adjusted in the simulation runs so as to match the targeted maximum temperature in the worst-case situation.

The number of parallel tapes is set to 10 for the 50 kVdc version where the I_c of the cable is 12.35 kA and the I_c of the SFCL is 11.5 kA. For the 25 kV version, with a I_c of the cable of 29.5 kA and the I_c of the SFCL of 23 kA, the number of tapes is set to 20.

The RSFCL also has a stray inductance, a hypothesis of 500 μH is fixed for the 50 kVdc version and 250 μH for the 25 kVdc version.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

3.10 Cable surge arrester

The SC cable as well as windfarm string cables are protected with pole to ground surge arresters. Especially it will protect the cable against overvoltage in case of pole to ground fault. Their clipping voltage is fixed at 1,6 pu, to be safely operate without heating under permanent voltage and protect the cable at an overvoltage lower than 2pu.

One outcome of the simulation plan will be the evaluation of the energy to be dissipated by these surge arresters.

4 FAULT SIMULATION

4.1 Pole to pole Fault

4.1.1 Fault F

4.1.1.1 Determination of the series reactor value

Following the principle of selective protection of the converters of the conversion station, a simulation plan is run to establish the correlation between the fault neutralization time, the arm reactor, the type of network (i.e. production or load) and the DCCB series reactor.

Figure 22 illustrates the 25 kVdc load case with a DCCB fault neutralisation time of 20 ms. The currents in all the converter DC breakers are plotted. In the steady state regime, they all carry -2500 A. when the fault happens between MMC1 poles, the current in DCCB1 (red curve) is reverted and is the sum of MMC2 to MMC7 contributions to the fault. After 20 ms, DCCB01s neutralizes the fault and isolates MMC1 from the others. The other MMCs remain under control, after the fault current is cleared, MMC2 to MMC7 reach a new steady state regime feeding the load via the SC cable. Figure 23 illustrate the case with a 50 kV production system, with a DCCB fault neutralisation time of 5 ms.

For a better understanding, Figure 20 shows the initial power flow and the fault current flow in the case of the Production Scheme, while Figure 21 shows the same but for the Consumption scheme.

Figure 20. Production scheme

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 21. Consumption scheme

Figure 22. Fault F, $U_n=25$ kVdc, consumption configuration, $t_{bk}=20$ ms. Red: DCCB_On1, Blue: DCCB_On2

Figure 23. Fault F, $U_n=50$ kVdc, production configuration, $t_{bk}=5$ ms. Red: DCCB_On1, Blue: DCCB_On2

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

The dimensioning of the series reactor shall also be verified in case breaker DCCB01 fails to clear. In that case, a trip order is sent to all the other DCCBs and the associated ACCB. During this time, the current continues increasing in the other healthy DCCBs and shall not exceed the target value of 16 kA.

This is illustrated in Figure 24 with the same case as Figure 23. The DCCBs 2 to 4 trip 10 ms (5 ms opening time of DCCB_{On1} + 5 ms breaker failure detection and relaying time) after the DCCB1 tripping and ACCB1 trips 70 ms (10 ms + 60 ms) after the fault F inception. In this case, it is confirmed that the current is interrupted below 16 kA by each of DCCB2 to DCCB4 and DCCB1 has to sustain a maximum of 30 kA as a short time peak current.

Figure 24. Fault F, $U_n=50$ kVdc, production configuration, $t_{bk}=5$ ms. Red: DCCB_On1, Blue: DCCB_On2

The table below summarizes the series DC reactor inductance values for the different operating cases:

Table 16: Series reactor values

U_n	kVDC	50	50	50	50	25	25	25	25
Variant	NA	Production	Production	Load	Load	Production	Production	Load	Load
L_{arm}	mH	6,88	6,88	6,88	6,88	3,44	3,44	3,44	3,44
I_{bk}	A	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000
t_{bk}	ms	5	20	5	20	5	20	5	20
L_{series}	mH	10,50	45,00	6,80	28,00	7,30	28,50	4,73	18,90

4.1.1.2 Impact on the DC CB

The fault F determines the maximum energy to be absorbed by the DCCB varistor. In case of non-opening of the DCCB, this fault also determines the maximum short time peak current withstand ($I_{stc,p}$) of the DCCB. Conclusions on these results are reported in 4.3

4.1.2 RSFCL worst case, Fault D4

The maximum energy to be absorbed by the RSFCL is for the fault D4. The worst case considers a failure of MMC01 DCCB.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

The maximum allowable temperature is set at 380 K giving a margin of 20% to the maximum theoretical temperature corresponding to fusion temperature of the PbSn alloy. The FCL characteristics being fixed as per 3.9, iterations are carried out to find the limitation length to match the maximum temperature. In [Table 17](#) are recorded the absorbed energy (E_n) as well as the required length (L_{lim}) of the RSFCL resulting of this fault case.

Table 17: RSFCL energy and limitation length

U_n	kVDC	50	50	50	50	25	25	25	25
Variant	NA	Production	Production	Load	Load	Production	Production	Load	Load
t_{bk}	ms	5	20	5	20	5	20	5	20
L_{lim}	m	833	765	753	933	66,7	224	191	449
E_n	KJ	21029	19451	19242	24240	3430	11359	9416	22608

The RSFCL sizing depends on the load flow direction, the prospective fault current rate of rise (interaction between source voltage and equivalent series inductance) and on the protection time. However, a certain homogeneity is visible for the 50 kV system with a gap of 26% between the minimum size and the maximum size. By contrast, for the 25 kV system, the ratio is 1 to 6,5.

4.1.3 SC cable fault

Owing to the SC cable model, it is possible to evaluate the SC cable fault current in case of faults D2, D1 and C. Additionally, fault B2 is regarded in the “Production” case.

The results are summarized with the hypothesis that the RSFCL 4.1.2 is in series and the DCCB of the converter MMC01 does not trip, as defined in 4.1.2

In the next sections, the fault current is measured between the RSFCL and converter cable extremity as shown on [Figure 25](#).

Figure 25. Location of short circuit current measurement. The convention used is that the current is positive when flowing from left to right.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.1.3.1 50 kVdc network

Table 18 summarizes the peak short circuit currents and RSFCL energies for the pole-to-pole faults D2, D1 and C considering a failure of MMC1 DCCB.

Table 18: 50 kVdc SC cable peak current for faults D2, D1 & C

Un	Variant	t_{bk}	D2 Ip w/o RSFCL	D2 Ip with RSFCL	D2 RSFCL Energy	D1 Ip	D1 RSFCL Energy	C Ip	C RSFCL Energy
[kV]	-	[ms]	[kAp]	[kAp]	[kJ]	[kAp]	[kJ]	[kAp]	[kJ]
50	Production	5	32,7	21,8	20904	13,8	5	9,3	0
50	Production	20	37	20,3	19450	16,3	36,5	9,3	0
50	Load	5	43,8	24,2	19214	20,9	21560	17,2	17543
50	Load	20	51	21,3	24038	19,9	25114	17,3	28284

From these results (RSFCL energy for the faults D1 and C), it can be seen that in the Production case, whether the protection time is 5 or 20 ms, the RSFCL will be almost transparent for fault at a distance of a few kms from the shore. This will be more illustrated in 4.1.3.1.1 and 4.1.3.1.2. In contrast, for the Consumption case, the RSFCL will always oppose a resistance even with a fault 100 km away from the shore and even for a short protection time of 5 ms. This will be more illustrated in 4.1.3.1.3 and 4.1.3.1.4. The reason for this difference is the current polarity reversal in case of fault that gives time for the protection to clip the fault current in the Production scenario. In the consumption scenario, the fault current is of the same polarity as the load current, therefore, the RSFCL is needed to efficiently limit the current.

In the following sections of 4.1.3.1, the plots will be related to the Negative Pole.

4.1.3.1.1 50 KVdc Production Case with protection time of 5 ms

Figure 26 shows the fault current for the 50 kV Production system with a protection time of 5 ms. The comparison between the faults D2 without and with RSFCL clearly shows a significant reduction of stress on the SC cable. Then, with faults D1 and C at a much longer distance from shore, the SC cable inductance is dominant to limit the fault current, the RSFCL does not quench for a fault distance as short as 25 km as shown on **Figure 27**.

Figure 26. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 27. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, the brunt of the fault current is supported mostly by the former and finally, the HTS layers reach up to 4 – 4,5 kA (above their critical current) but only for a very short time. The presence of the RSFCL makes only a small difference for the HTS layers peak current, as shown in Figure 28 and Figure 29 it makes much more difference in the decay time of the HTS current. The presence of the series resistance of the RSFCL allows a much faster discharge of the magnetic energy of the network.

Figure 28. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

Figure 29. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.1.3.1.2 50 KVdc Production Case with protection time of 20 ms

Figure 30 shows the fault current for the 50 kV Production system with a protection time of 20 ms. The comparison between the faults D2 without and with RSFCL clearly shows a significant reduction of stress on the SC cable. Then, with faults D1 and C at a much longer distance from shore, the SC cable inductance is dominant to limit the fault current, even though the RSFCL dissipates a little bit of energy for a fault distant of 25 km as shown on Figure 31.

Figure 30. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 31. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, the brunt of the fault current is supported mostly by the former and finally, the HTS layers reach up to 4 – 4,5 kA (above their critical current) but only for a very short time. The presence of the RSFCL makes only a small difference for the HTS layers peak current as shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33 it makes much more difference in the decay time of the HTS current, the presence of the series resistance of the RSFCL allowing a much faster discharge of the magnetic energy of the network.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 32. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

Figure 33. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

4.1.3.1.3 50 KVdc Consumption Case with protection time of 5 ms

Figure 34 shows the fault current for the 50 kV Consumption system with a protection time of 5 ms. In contrast to the production Case, the fault current profiles for D2, D1 and C with the RSFCL are similar, indicating that the RSFCL quenches including for the case C. This is clearly shown in Figure 35.

Figure 34. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 35. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, the brunt of the fault current is supported mostly by the former and finally, the HTS layers reach up to 6 – 6,5 kA (above their critical current) but again only for a short time. The presence of the RSFCL makes only a small difference for the HTS layers peak current as shown in Figure 36 and Figure 37 - it makes much more difference in the decay time of the HTS current, the presence of the series resistance of the RSFCL allowing a much faster discharge of the magnetic energy of the network.

Figure 36. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

Figure 37. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 38 shows that thanks to the RSFCL, the HTS layer resistances are reduced thus limiting their heating.

Figure 38. 500 m SC cable portion: HTS layer resistances for D2 without RSFCL (left) and D2 with RSFCL (right). HTS1 (Red), HTS2 (Blue), HTS3 (Green), HTS4 (Pink)

4.1.3.1.4 50 KVdc Consumption Case with protection time of 20 ms

Figure 39 shows the fault current for the 50 kV Consumption system with a protection time of 20 ms. The comparison between the faults D2 without and with RSFCL clearly shows a significant reduction of stress on the SC cable. As for a protection time of 5 ms, the current profiles for faults D2, D1 and C with the RSFCL are very similar. In these cases, the RSFCL quenches and protects the network even for the Fault C as shown in Figure 40.

Figure 39. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 40. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, the brunt of the fault current is supported mostly by the former and finally, the HTS layers reach up to 5 – 5,5 kA (above their critical current) but only for a very short time. The presence of the RSFCL makes only a small difference for the HTS layers peak current as shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33 it makes much more difference in the decay time of the HTS current, the presence of the series resistance of the RSFCL allowing a much faster discharge of the magnetic energy of the network.

Figure 41. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

Figure 42. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), HTS1 (Blue), HTS2 (Green), HTS3 (Pink), HTS4 (Orange), Shield (Dark Blue). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 43 shows that thanks to the RSFCL, the HTS layer resistances are reduced, thus limiting their heating.

Figure 43. 500 m SC cable portion: HTS layer resistances for D2 without RSFCL (left) and D2 with RSFCL (right). HTS1 (Red), HTS2 (Blue), HTS3 (Green), HTS4 (Pink)

4.1.3.2 25 kVdc network

Table 19 summarizes the peak short circuit currents and RSFCL energies for the pole-to-pole faults D2, D1 and C considering a failure of MMC1 DCCB.

Table 19: 25 kVdc SC cable peak current for faults D2, D1 & C

Un	Variant	t_{bk}	Cable structure	D2 Ip w/o RSFCL	D2 Ip with RSFCL	D2 RSFCL Energy	D1 Ip	D1 RSFCL Energy	C Ip	C RSFCL Energy
[kV]	-	[ms]	-	[kAp]	[kAp]	[kJ]	[kAp]	[kJ]	[kAp]	[kJ]
25	Production	5	Concentric	42	35	5,6	12,6	0	3,9	0
25	Production	20	Concentric	59,4	40,5	10933	11,6	0	6,6	0
25	Production	5	Petal	42,6	30,9	0	13,1	0	5,3	0
25	Production	20	Petal	59,4	41	10687	11,8	0	7,3	0
25	Load	5	Concentric	84,1	48	9197	31,5	9,6	26,3	0
25	Load	20	Concentric	93,4	40,7	22770	32,6	17426	28,4	5,3
25	Load	5	Petal	83,9	47,4	9192	32,3	10,4	26	0
25	Load	20	Petal	87,1	40,9	22712	32	12743	29,3	6,2

From these results, it can be seen that in the Production case, with a protection time of 5 ms, the RSFCL is transparent and therefore of no interest. With a protection time of 20 ms the RSFCL is helpful for faults at short distance but becomes transparent after a few kilometres. The picture is different for the Consumption case where, even with a short protection time of 5 ms, the RSFCL has an impact for the short distance fault. The role of the RSFCL is even more prominent with a protection time of 20 ms and with faults at distances higher than 25 km.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

In the following sections of 4.1.3.2, the plots will be related to the Positive Pole.

4.1.3.2.1 25 KVdc Production Case – Concentric cable - 5 ms Protection time

Figure 44 shows that in this configuration, the RSFCL has no impact on the fault current. That is consistent with Table 17, where the RSFCL length was very short for this configuration.

Figure 44. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, when there is no RSFCL, the current is quickly commuted from the MgB_2 layer to the former, whereas when there is a RSFCL, the current is shared between the MgB_2 layer and the former.

Figure 45. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2 without RSFCL (left) and with RSFCL (right): distribution of currents. Former (Red), MgB_2 layer (Blue), Shield (Green)

This results in a higher MgB_2 layer resistance in the case without RSFCL compared to the case with RSFCL, as it can be seen on Figure 46, but it remains at very low values.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 46. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance for D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

4.1.3.2.2 25 KVdc Production Case – Petal cable - 5 ms Protection time

For the Petal cable, the outcome is the same as for the concentric cable: in the Production scenario, the protection time of 5 ms makes the RSFCL inoperant. This is shown in [Figure 47](#).

Figure 47. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, it can be seen in [Figure 48](#), without RSFCL, the current is shared between the MgB₂ layer, the former and the petal centre core and it takes more than 300 ms to reach current zero in these layers. In contrary, with the RSFCL, only the MgB₂ layers carries the current.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 48. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2 without RSFCL (left) and with RSFCL (right). Former (Red), Petal centre (Blue), MgB₂ (Green), Shield (Pink)

This translates in the development of a resistance by the MgB₂ layer for the fault D2 without RSFCL, whereas no resistance is developed by the MgB₂ layer when the RSFCL is in series as shown in [Figure 49](#).

Figure 49. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

4.1.3.2.3 25 KVdc Production Case – Concentric cable - 20 ms Protection time

[Figure 50](#) shows the impact of the RSFCL on Fault D2 with and without FCL and then the reduction of the peak current with long distance faults D1 and C. [Figure 51](#) shows the RSFCL is influent on Fault D2 and it is not any more for faults D1 and C where the cable inductance dominates to limit the fault current.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 50. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 51. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, it can be seen in [Figure 52](#) that the MgB₂ layer quenches and commutes the current to the former when there is no RSFCL and the current is shared between the MgB₂ layer and the former when there is a RSFCL.

Figure 52. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2 without RSFCL (left) and with RSFCL (right): distribution of currents. Former (Red), MgB₂ layer (Blue), Shield (Green)

This results in a higher MgB₂ layer resistance in the case without RSFCL compared to the case with RSFCL as it can be seen on [Figure 53](#) but it remains at very low values.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 53. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

4.1.3.2.4 25 KVdc Production Case – Petal cable - 20 ms Protection time

Figure 54 shows the impact of the RSFCL on Fault D2 with and without FCL and then the reduction of the peak current with long distance faults D1 and C. Figure 55 shows the RSFCL is influent on Fault D2 and it is not any more for faults D1 and C where the cable inductance dominates to limit the fault current.

Figure 54. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 55. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, it can be seen in [Figure 56](#), without RSFCL, the current is shared between the MgB2 layer, the former and the petal centre core. Whereas, in [Figure 57](#), with the RSFCL, the MgB2 layer quickly bears the cable current but for a much shorter time than without RSFCL.

Figure 56. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), Petal centre (Blue), MgB2 (Green), Shield (Pink)

Figure 57. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), Petal centre (Blue), MgB2 (Green), Shield (Pink)

This translates in the development of a resistance by the MgB2 layer for the fault D2 without RSFCL, whereas no resistance is developed by the MgB2 layer when the RSFCL is in series as shown in [Figure 58](#).

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 58. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

4.1.3.2.5 25 KVdc Consumption Case – Concentric cable - 5 ms Protection time

Figure 59 shows the impact of the RSFCL on Fault D2 with and without FCL and then the reduction of the peak current with long distance faults D1 and C. Figure 60 shows the RSFCL is influent on Fault D2 and it is not any more for faults D1 and C where the cable inductance dominates to limit the fault current.

Figure 59. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 60. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, it can be seen in [Figure 61](#) and [Figure 62](#) that the MgB₂ layer quenches and commutes the current to the former whether the RSFCL is in series of the cable or not.

Figure 61. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), MgB₂ layer (Blue), Shield (Green). The right figure is a zoom of the left figure.

Figure 62. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), MgB₂ layer (Blue), Shield (Green)

By plotting ([Figure 63](#)) the resistance of the MgB₂ layer, it comes out that D1 is a dangerous situation, with the MgB₂ layer slowly building resistance without the RSFCL preventing it.

Figure 63. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.1.3.2.6 25 KVdc Consumption Case – Petal cable - 5 ms Protection time

Figure 64 shows the impact of the RSFCL on Fault D2 with and without FCL and then the reduction of the peak current with long distance faults D1 and C. Figure 65 shows the RSFCL is influent on Fault D2 and it is not any more for faults D1 and C where the cable inductance dominates to limit the fault current.

Figure 64. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 65. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, it can be seen in Figure 66, without RSFCL, the current is shared between the MgB2 layer, the former and the petal centre core. Whereas, in Figure 67, with the RSFCL, the MgB2 layer quickly bears the cable current. In the Petal configuration, there is no full current commutation from the MgB2 layer to the other conductors as it was observed in the Concentric cable (4.1.3.2.5).

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 66. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), Petal centre (Blue), MgB₂ (Green), Shield (Pink)

Figure 67. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), Petal centre (Blue), MgB₂ (Green), Shield (Pink)

Again, in Figure 68 it can be seen that a resistance is built by the MgB₂ layer when there is no RSFCL, whereas, when the RSFCL is present, the MgB₂ layer is not resistive.

Figure 68. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.1.3.2.7 25 KVdc Consumption Case – Concentric cable - 20 ms Protection time

Figure 69 shows the fault current for the 25 kV Consumption system with the Concentric type Cable and a protection time of 20 ms. Curves of fault D2 with RSFCL and D1 are similar, indicating the RSFCL is effective for the D1 case as well. Figure 70 confirms that the RSFCL is active for a fault located 25 km away.

Figure 69. Short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 70. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, it can be seen in [Figure 71](#) and [Figure 72](#) that the MgB₂ layer quenches and commutes the current to the former whether the RSFCL is in series of the cable or not. However, with a RSFCL, the MgB₂ layer current decays faster to zero in 10 ms versus 20 ms inducing a lower heating.

Figure 71. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), MgB₂ layer (Blue), Shield (Green)

Figure 72. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), MgB₂ layer (Blue), Shield (Green)

This time, when we compare to 4.1.3.2.5, [Figure 68](#) shows that the RSFCL is more effective for the Fault D2 (the MgB₂ layer resistance is roughly divided by two when the RSFCL is inserted). But the weak point is no longer fault D1 but fault C.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 73. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

4.1.3.2.8 25 KVdc Consumption Case – Petal cable - 20 ms Protection time

Figure 74 shows the fault current for the 25 kV Consumption system with the Petal type Cable and with a protection time of 20 ms. Figure 75 indicates that the RSFCL is effective for faults D2 and D1 as well.

Figure 74. short circuit current, faults D2 without RSFCL (red) / D2 with RSFCL (Blue) / D1 with RSFCL (Green) / C with RSFCL (Pink)

Figure 75. RSFCL energy D2 (Red) / D1 (Blue) / C (Green)

As regards the distribution of current inside the SC cable, for the fault D2, the general picture is the same as for the 5 ms protection time: without RSFCL, the current is shared between the MgB₂ layer, the former and the petal centre core. With the RSFCL, the MgB₂ layer bears the current.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 76. 500 m SC cable portion, fault D2: distribution of currents without RSFCL. Former (Red), Petal Centre (Blue), MgB₂ layer (Green), Shield (Pink)

Figure 77. 500 m SC cable portion, Fault D2: distribution of currents with RSFCL. Former (Red), Petal Centre (Blue), MgB₂ layer (Green), Shield (Pink)

Figure 78 shows that the RSFCL is efficient for the Fault D2 (the MgB₂ layer resistance is suppressed when the RSFCL is inserted). There remains a weak point with the Fault D1 contrary with the protection time of 5 ms (4.1.3.2.6).

Figure 78. 500 m SC cable portion, MgB₂ layer resistance. D2 without RSFCL (Red), D2 with RSFCL (Blue), D1 with RSFCL (Green), C with RSFCL (Pink)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.1.4 Wind mill cluster string cable fault B2

With this fault, it is possible to evaluate if a selective strategy can be applied by isolating the faulty link keeping the other sources in operation. This can define if a slow or a fast breaker is necessary and if a series reactor is required as well. Indeed, the long length of a cable will necessary strongly slow down the current contributed from the AC grid source; therefore, quick response and additional series inductance might not be necessary.

No series reactor is implemented and a slow breaker with a fault current neutralization time of 20 ms is modelled.

The primary protection consists in operating only the respective faulty string cable DC breaker. In a second step, a DC CB failure is considered where all the other offshore DCCBs will be tripped as well as the onshore DCCBs.

4.1.4.1 50 kVdc system

The simulations are performed with DCCB_Off01 neutralizing current in 20 ms. On the converter side, the neutralization time is either 5 ms or 20 ms. At first, a normal operation of DCCB_Off01 is considered, so the protection time of the DCCB converters only plays via the converter branch series inductance.

Figure 79 shows that the power flow is recovered after the fault clearance by DCCB_Off01 with a reduced power because of the loss of 200 MW.

Figure 79. SC cable current with converter DC CBs protection time of 5 ms (Red) and 20 ms (Blue)

Figure 80 shows a high frequency inrush current in DCCB_Off01 of 55 kAp at the instant of the fault that decays in less than 2 ms. The current prior to interruption is 11,6 kA and it is well below the 16-kA threshold.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 80. DCCB_Off01 current with converter DC CBs protection time of 5 ms (Red) and 20 ms (Blue)

Figure 81 shows the energy dissipated by the DCCB_Off01 ZnO does not exceed 110 kJ for the 5 ms protection time case and is limited to 25 kJ for the 20 ms protection time case.

Figure 81. DCCB_Off01 ZnO energy with converter DC CBs protection time of 5 ms (Red) and 20 ms (Blue)

The next simulation aims at verifying the system behaviour in case of failure of DCCB_Off01. In that case, all offshore DCCBs will trip as well as all onshore converter DC CBs. Figure 82 shows the current interruption on the SC cable (left) and the DCCB_Off01 short time current to sustain before interruption by all the other DCCBs (right).

Figure 82. Left: SC cable current with 5 ms (Red) and 20 ms (Blue) protection time. Right: Same for DCCB_Off01 current

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

To conclude, it is shown that on the offshore side, “Slow” mechanical DCCBs are sufficient to manage the selectivity in case of string cable fault and this without need of a series reactor. Its specification of short circuit current performance can be set at 15 kA to keep a margin of 20% as for the onshore DCCB. The ZnO has to be sized for at least 110 kJ. Its short time withstand capability has to be set to 55 kAp.

4.1.4.2 25 kVdc system

The same principle is applied for the 25 kVdc system.

Figure 83 shows the power flow is recovered after the fault clearance by DCCB_Off01 with a reduced power because of the loss of 200 MW. The cases with Concentric cable and Petal configuration are shown as well as 5 ms and 20 ms Protection time. No difference can be detected except in the high frequency superimposed current.

Figure 83. SC cable current with converter DC CBs protection time of 5 ms (Red – Concentric, Green - Petal) and 20 ms (Blue – Concentric, Pink - Petal)

Figure 84 shows a high frequency inrush current in DCCB_Off01 of 39 kAp at the instant of the fault that decays in roughly 10 ms. The petal cable induces a slightly higher inrush current than the Concentric cable, but the difference is less than 6%. The current prior to interruption results equal to 5,6 kA and it is well below the 16-kA threshold.

Figure 84. DCCB_Off01 current with converter DC CBs protection time of 5 ms (Red – Concentric, Green - Petal) and 20 ms (Blue – Concentric, Pink - Petal)

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 85 shows the transient voltage across DCCB_Off01; it illustrates that the peak voltage does not exceed 1.6 pu, therefore, the ZnO is not triggered.

Figure 85. DCCB_Off01 ZnO energy with converter DC CBs protection time of 5 ms (Red – Concentric, Green - Petal) and 20 ms (Blue – Concentric, Pink - Petal)

The next simulation aims at verifying the system behaviour in case of failure of DCCB_Off01. In that case, all offshore DCCBs will trip as well as all onshore converter DC CBs. Figure 86 shows the current interruption on the SC cable (left) and the DCCB_Off01 short time current to sustain before the interruption by all the other DCCBs (right).

Figure 86. Left: SC cable current with 5 ms (Red-Concentric, Green-Petal) and 20 ms (Blue-Concentric, Pink-Petal) protection time. Right: Same for the DCCB_Off01 current

To conclude for the 50 kVdc system, it has been shown that on the offshore side, “Slow” mechanical DCCBs are sufficient to manage the selectivity in case of a string cable fault and this can be achieved without the need of a series reactor.

Its specification of short circuit current performance can be set at 7,5 kA to get a margin of 20% and possibly no ZnO is required, but it can be kept anyway for safety criteria. Its short time withstand capability has to be set to 40 kAp.

4.2 Pole to Ground Fault

Both SC cable extremities are equipped with a pole to ground varistor (ZnO).

Pole to ground faults are simulated at 3 locations along the SC cable: D4, *i.e.* the offshore cable end; C, *i.e.* the offshore cable end and D1, 25 km away from the onshore cable end. The fault is created on Pole P, the target is to limit the overvoltage of Pole N to less than 1.8 pu and to evaluate the absorbed

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

energy by the protecting ZnO. The cases are simulated with a protection time of 5 ms for the Onshore DCCBs and 20 ms for the Offshore DCCBs.

Voltage and Current measurements shown in the next sections refer to **Figure 87**, the offshore side is on the left and the onshore side is on the right of the figure.

Figure 87. Schematic with voltage and current measurements

4.2.1 50 kVdc Production case

Figure 88 represents the SC cable current with the superposition of D4, D1 and C faults.

On top of the figure, the Onshore side current is displayed, while the offshore side current is shown in the bottom part.

Figure 88. SC cable current: onshore side (top) and offshore side (bottom)

As regards the offshore side current, it has to be reminded that the windmill converters are controlled to maintain a constant current even in case of a fault.

4.2.1.1 Fault D4 at the onshore extremity of SC cable

Figure 89 shows the Pole P and Pole N voltages at both extremities of the cable. On the left, the Positive Pole voltage is shown, whereas, on the right, the Negative Pole voltage is shown.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

With the fault on D4, it will take roughly 100 ms for the Pole P voltage of the offshore cable extremity to reach voltage zero. As regards Pole N, the maximum voltage reaches 1.76 pu on the onshore side, before reaching back the system voltage. Since the cable is not resistive, the charge trapped in the SC cable capacitance cannot be evacuated unless, for example, a grounding switch is used to force the pole to ground voltage.

Figure 90 shows the 2 ZnO energies amounting for the onshore side to 13.2 MJ.

Figure 89. Left: pole P cable ends voltages, Right: pole N cable ends voltages

Figure 90. ZnO energies: Blue – Onshore side, Red – Offshore side

4.2.1.2 Fault D1, 25 km away from the onshore cable extremity

Figure 91 shows the Pole P and Pole N voltages at both extremities of the cable. On the left, the Positive Pole voltage is shown, whereas, on the right, the Negative Pole voltage is shown.

With the fault on D1, it will take roughly 100 ms for the Pole P voltage of the onshore cable extremity to reach voltage zero. As regards Pole N, the maximum voltage reaches 1.79 pu on the onshore side and 1.74 on the offshore side, before reaching a steady state voltage of 32 kVdc. As suggested in the case of fault D4, a grounding switch could be used to force the pole to ground voltage.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 92 shows the 2 ZnO energies amounting for the onshore side to 12.8 MJ.

Figure 91. Left: pole P cable ends voltages, Right: pole N cable ends voltages

Figure 92. ZnO energies: Blue – Onshore side, Red – Offshore side

4.2.1.3 Fault C at the offshore extremity of SC cable

Figure 93 shows the Pole P and Pole N voltages at both extremities of the cable. On the left of the figure, the Positive Pole voltage is shown, whereas, on the right, the Negative Pole voltage is shown.

When a Fault C occurs, it will take roughly 100 ms for the Pole P voltage of the onshore cable extremity to reach voltage zero. As regards Pole N, the maximum voltage reaches 1.75 pu on both the onshore and offshore sides, before reaching a steady state voltage of 23 kVdc. Again, as seen earlier, a grounding switch could be used to force the pole to ground voltage.

Figure 94 shows the 2 ZnO energies amounting for the onshore side to 11.3 MJ.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 93. Left: pole P cable ends voltages, Right: pole N cable ends voltages

Figure 94. ZnO energies (Blue – Onshore side, Red – Offshore side)

4.2.2 25 kVdc Production case

Only the Concentric cable is simulated. The same approach adopted on the 50 kV system is developed. The same type of observations is made as for instance the residual trapped charge on Pole N that could be discharged using a grounding switch.

Figure 95 represents the Positive and Negative Pole voltages with Faults D4, D1 and C.

The worst overvoltage peak on Pole N is equal to 1.64 pu.

Figure 97 shows the ZnO energies: the ZnO on the onshore side has to absorb up to 26 MJ for the fault D4 and the ZnO on the offshore side has to absorb up to 1,2 MJ for the fault D1.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

Figure 95. Positive Pole Voltage: Red – Onshore side, Blue – Offshore side for faults D4 (left), D1 (centre), and C (right)

Figure 96. Negative Pole Voltage: Red – Onshore side, Blue – Offshore side for faults D4 (left), D1 (centre), and C (right)

Figure 97. SC cable ZnO energies offshore (left) and onshore (right). Red: Fault D4, Blue: Fault D1, Green: Fault C

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

4.3 Synthesis on the DCCBs

The fault F (4.1.1) determines the maximum energy to be absorbed by the varistor of the conversion station DCCBs as well as their short time peak current withstand ($I_{stc,p}$). Table 20 reports these results for the different system voltages and load flow cases.

Table 20: Converter station DCCB characteristics

U_n	kVDC	50	50	50	50	25	25	25	25
Variant	NA	Production	Production	Load	Load	Production	Production	Load	Load
U_{prot}	pu	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,6
I_{bk}	A	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000	16000
t_{bk}	ms	5	20	5	20	5	20	5	20
$I_{stc,p}$	kA	34,8	27,6	29,1	27,5	38	30,7	41,6	32,5
Energy	KJ	4288	17003	1998	7473	2478	10102	1270	5104

The fault B2 (4.1.4) determines the maximum energy to be absorbed by the varistor of the offshore DCCB, it also determines its required breaking current and short time peak current withstand ($I_{stc,p}$). Table 21 reports the results for the different system voltages and conversion station DCCB fault neutralisation time cases.

Table 21: Offshore DCCB characteristics

U_n	kVDC	50	50	25	25
U_{prot}	pu	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,6
Offshore DCCB t_{bk}	ms	20	20	20	20
Conversion station t_{bk}	ms	5	20	5	20
I_{bk}	A	11600	10250	5850	5500
TIV	pu	1,6	1,55	1,37	1
$I_{stc,p}$	kA	54,9	55	35,8	36,1
Energy	KJ	110	25,3	1	0

Not only the offshore DCCB can be a “slow” mechanical DC CB, but its breaking performance requirement is also reduced from 16 kA to 12 kA for the 50 kV system and from 16 kA to 6 kA for the 25 kV system. Also, its energy dissipation requirement is marginal, not exceeding 110 kJ for the worst case.

5 CONCLUSION

The work carried out in this Deliverable delineated the guidelines for the protection of a MVDC superconducting link. The detailed modelling of the converters, the mechanical DCCB, the multiphysics modelling of the SC cable and the RSFCL were implemented in the EMTP-RV environment. Each cable variant was deeply modelled to take into account the different transition scenarios from superconductive to resistive states that can happen after a short circuit fault. A key input data in the EMTP-RV modelling of the SC cable was also the direct and mutual inductance matrix dictating the internal current repartition together with the resistive and nonlinear resistive components of each conductor.

A mapping of pole-to-pole faults into the production cluster, the converter station or on the load side and into the cable was established. A methodology was applied to fix the dimensions of the converter series reactors and of the RSFCL before simulating the faults in the cable and elsewhere. In the case of production clusters, the short circuit current is in the opposite direction compared to the initial power flow while for the consumption case the short circuit current has the same direction. This has a direct impact on protection design as shown by the conclusions depicted below.

For a fault on the offshore windfarm cluster, a selective fault clearing can be applied using offshore slow mechanical DC circuit breakers (fault neutralization time of 20 ms) without additional series inductance. For these breakers, the parallel surge arrester is light in the sense that the energy to be absorbed will be modest (around 100 kJ) because the fault current contribution coming from the wind farm and cable connection is limited.

For a fault on a converter station is also possible to consider a selective fault clearing to isolate the faulty converter branch. To do so, a mechanical DC Circuit breaker in series with an inductance (up to 45 mH) can manage this selectivity function. The inductance value is directly related to the DCCB fault neutralization time; a faster DCCB fault neutralization time (e.g. 5 ms) allows a lower inductance value (up to 10 mH). Disregarding other aspects, selecting the optimum DCCB neutralization time and reactor size would require a deeper techno-economic analysis. It is worth noting that for this type of fault the RSFCL is not quenching because the contribution from the offshore side is limited.

For a fault into the cable, the protection design is dependent on the system voltage and SC cable design choices:

- In the case of the 50 kVdc system:
 - The protection time (fault neutralization time) does not make much difference on the RSFCL size whether a production case or a consumption case is considered: the RSFCL energy varies by 26% between its minimum value and its maximum value.
 - The RSFCL allows a significant reduction of the short circuit peak current into the cable (a factor between 1.5 and 2.4) and therefore a reduction of the electrodynamic forces it has to sustain.
 - For the production case, the RSFCL quenches for cable faults close to the RSFCL (few tens of km), while for the consumption case the RSFCL quenches even for faults located 100 km away from the RSFCL.

D5.2: Specifications of protection devices

- Looking at the SC cable internal currents, the transient currents of the HTS layers briefly exceed their critical current even if no RSFCL is inserted in series.
- In the case of the 25 kVdc system:
 - For the production case, with a fault neutralization time of 5 ms, the RSFCL is not needed because it has no impact on the short circuit peak current (the DCCB operates before the quenching of the RSFCL).
 - For the consumption case:
 - The RSFCL allows a significant reduction of the short circuit peak current into the cable (a factor between 1.7 and 2.3) and therefore a reduction of the electrodynamic forces it has to sustain.
 - The RSFCL quenches for cable faults close to the RSFCL (few tens of km) but not for distant faults (e.g. 100 km away).
 - The cable configuration (petal or concentric) has an impact on the protection design. As an example, for a fault 25 km away from RSFCL, the concentric cable shows a risk of thermal runaway that is not observed in the petal configuration. This has to be further analysed and confirmed by SC cable manufacturer.

Finally, pole-to-ground faults were simulated in view of evaluating the SC cable protection ZnO energy and their ability to limit the overvoltages of the non-faulty pole.

The obtained results will be used by manufacturers for the detail designs of SC cable and protection devices within the relevant SCARLET work packages.

6 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] C. Creusot, P.-B. Steckler, A. Bertinato, A. Morandi, «SCARLET Deliverable D5.1 Selection of electrical system architecture».
- [2] C. Creusot, A. Morandi, F. Mimmi, E. Guerra, A. Bertinato, P.-B. Steckler, P. L. Ribani, M. Fabbri, M. Bocchi, A. Musso, G. Angeli, D. Brasiliano, “Superconducting Cable Modelling into Electro-Magnetic Transient Simulation Tool,” *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, 2024.
- [3] U. o. W. Robinson Research Institute, «High-Temperature superconducting wire critical current database,» 2024. [En línea]. Available: <https://htsdb.wimbush.eu/>.
- [4] S. C. a. Z. J. Jiamin Zhu, «Progress on Second-Generation High-Temperature Superconductor Tape Targeting Resistive Fault Current Limiter Application,» *mdpi electronics*, 2022.
- [5] SuperGrid Institute, «NSWPH Validation Technical Requirements,» *North Sea Wind Power Hub*, 2022.